

Joint Stiffness Effects on the Trajectories of Underactuated Robots

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Abstract—The paper discusses underactuated robots that possess fewer actuators compared to their degrees of freedom. These robots incorporate torsional springs in non-actuated joints and can accomplish point-to-point motions. The trajectory of these robots is influenced by the torsional stiffness of their joints. Specifically, the paper focuses on analyzing a 3-degree-of-freedom (DOF) robot equipped with two actuators and a torsional spring. It investigates the impact of joint stiffness on the robot's behavior and motion characteristics. Additionally, the paper presents a comparison of the swept area between the underactuated robot and an equivalent fully actuated robot. The findings indicate reductions in the swept area of up to 36% for the underactuated robot when compared to its fully actuated counterpart.

Index Terms—Underactuated systems; Joint stiffness; Trajectory; Robots

I. INTRODUCTION

Underactuated robots have gained popularity due to their ability to gain dexterity with low-cost and low-weight structures. In fact, underactuated robots are manipulators with one or more non-actuated joints, and often, the actuators are substituted by torsional springs [1].

Controlling the dynamics of a robot can be challenging due to the nonlinearity typically present in such systems. When the number of degrees of freedom (DOF) exceeds the number of actuators, the control becomes even more difficult. However, researchers have explored the concept of differential flatness as a potential solution. Differential flatness refers to systems that have specific outputs, known as "flat outputs," from which all states and inputs, including actuators' torques, can be determined without the need for integration [2].

In a differentially flat system, the number of flat outputs is equal to the number of inputs, i.e., the actuator torques. For a planar robot to be considered differentially flat, it needs to satisfy certain conditions [3].

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF A 3-DOF ROBOT

The robot presented in this paper is differentially flat. The schematic representation of the planar robot with 3-DOF is

depicted in Figure 1. The robot consists of two actuated joints and one passive joint. To account for friction in the non-actuated joint, a viscous damper (with a viscous coefficient c_3) is connected in parallel with the torsional spring (with a stiffness of k_3). The dynamics of the robot are linear because the last two joints are fully balanced. The equations of motion are as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_1^* & I_2^* & I_3^* \\ I_2^* & I_2^* & I_3^* \\ I_3^* & I_3^* & I_3^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{q}_1 \\ \ddot{q}_2 \\ \ddot{q}_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ c_3\dot{q}_3 + k_3q_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_1 \\ \tau_2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The flat variables are defined as follows:

$$y_1 = q_1 + q_2 + q_3 \quad (2)$$

$$y_2 = q_1 \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1: Scheme of the 3-DOF robot.

The motor torques are:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_1(t) &= \tau_2(t) + (I_1^* - I_2^*)\ddot{y}_2 \\ \tau_2(t) &= I_2^*\ddot{y}_1 + \frac{I_3^*(I_2^* - I_3^*)}{k_3}y_1^{(4)} - \frac{c_3I_3^*(I_2^* - I_3^*)}{k_3^2}y_1^{(5)} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

III. EFFECT OF JOINT STIFFNESS ON TRAJECTORIES

To assess the influence of joint stiffness of the final non-actuated joint, several simulations were conducted. These simulations maintained a consistent motion time of $t_f = 0.6$ seconds while varying the stiffness of the non-actuated joint, denoted as k_3 , within the range $(1.5 \div 5.0 \times 10^{-3}, \text{Nm/rad})$.

Figure 2 shows the end-effector trajectories obtained considering different stiffness values. When higher values of stiffness

Fig. 2: End-effector trajectories obtaining different stiffness values and the same motion time (0.6 s).

are considered, the end-effector trajectories closely resemble an arc of a circumference. This arc represents the trajectory of an equivalent 2-DOF robot that lacks the non-actuated joint but has an adjusted length for the last link, denoted as $a'_2 = a_2 + a_3$. As the torsional stiffness decreases, the central portion of the trajectory undergoes modifications characterized by a reduction in the swept area and the formation of a protrusion. In the case of higher stiffness values, the protrusion tends to form a cusp. Eventually, with extremely low torsional stiffness values, the protrusion degenerates into a loop. This loop is connected to the initial and final parts of the trajectory through two smaller loops.

Figure 3 shows the total area swept by the robot considering two torsional stiffness, $k_3 = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ Nm/rad}$, $k_3 = 5.0 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ Nm/rad}$ and the same motion time ($t_f = 0.6 \text{ s}$). The red trajectory is the trajectory of the tip of the end-effector, whereas the blue trajectory is the trajectory of the back-end of the third link (with the counterbalance).

During the motion, the robot primarily moves within the third and fourth quadrants. The torsional stiffness has minimal influence on the areas swept by the robot in these quadrants. However, as the torsional stiffness decreases, the swept area in the first and second quadrants is reduced. This change transforms the area from a semicircle, which corresponds to the largest stiffness values, into a shape with three lobes. This characteristic can be advantageous when operating the robot in the presence of obstacles located in these areas. A numerical method was developed to quantitatively evaluate the swept area. A comparison is made between the areas swept by the underactuated robot and those swept by an equivalent fully

Fig. 3: Areas swept by the robot considering four different stiffness values with the same motion time ($t_f = 0.6 \text{ s}$): (a) $k = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ Nm/rad}$, (b) $k = 5.0 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ Nm/rad}$. The white dots identify the tip and the back-end of the last link.

actuated 2-degree-of-freedom (2-DOF) robot. The equivalent robot has a last link length equal to the sum of links 2 and 3: $a'_2 = a_2 + a_3$. It is worth noting that when the underactuated robot is equipped with a low-stiffness spring, the reduction in the swept area can reach approximately 36%.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a comprehensive study on a planar 3-DOF underactuated robot that is differentially flat. The last joint of the robot is equipped with a torsional spring in parallel with a torsional damper to account for friction losses. A specific mathematical model, exploiting the properties of differential flatness in the Laplace domain, was developed to calculate the motor torques.

Parametric calculations were conducted to examine the impact of torsional spring stiffness on the robot's trajectories. The study showcases the advantages of employing a partially actuated system over a fully actuated one, including the utilization of fewer motors and the reduction in the area swept by the robot's links during its task execution.

It was found that significant reductions in the swept area can be achieved by decreasing the stiffness of the non-actuated joint. However, this approach results in increased motor torques, particularly τ_2 , which need to be carefully evaluated in terms of energy consumption and motor constraints. A more in-depth analysis is presented in [5].

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